

Supplementary tables

Supplementary Table 1. List of bivalve species and body size parameters recorded by

each stratigraphic unit. Mean: Average body size per species (mm), n = number of individuals measured, S.D.= Standard deviation per species, Min. = Minimum body size per species and Max.= Maximum body size per species.

Westbury Formation					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	8.3	14	3.01	4.67	15.98
<i>Cassianella</i> sp.	3.39	4	1.06	2.57	4.85
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	17.55	56	7.83	4.98	40.48
<i>Dacryomya</i> sp.	4.86	1	***	4.86	4.86
<i>Isocyprina concentricum</i> (Moore)	8.01	101	4.02	1.94	36.91
<i>Isocyprina ewaldi</i> (Bornemann)	8.00	12	2.56	3.82	11.70
<i>Liostrea bristovi</i> (Richardson)	17.21	16	6.33	8.93	31.38
<i>Modiolus hillanus</i> (J. Sowerby)	10.59	9	6.73	3.31	26.36
<i>Modiolus sodburiensis</i> (Reynolds & Vaughan)	8.12	21	3.17	4.04	16.87
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	8.26	19	3.37	2.79	13.31
<i>Myoconcha psilonoti</i> Quenstedt	17.95	1	***	17.95	17.95
<i>Mytilus cloacinus</i> Tutcher	9.56	11	2.77	6.18	14.80
<i>Permophorus elongatus</i> (Moore)	11.87	71	3.95	4.25	26.73
<i>Placunopsis alpina</i> (Winkler)	23.63	26	10.73	7.52	50.21
<i>Plagiostoma punctatum</i> J. Sowerby	21.23	9	5.82	11.74	30.73
<i>Protocardia rhaetica</i> (Merian)	10.48	11	4.42	5.32	17.47
<i>Pteromya crowcombeia</i> Moore	6.79	33	1.88	4.37	11.13
<i>Rhaetavicula contorta</i> (Portlock)	9.05	191	3.30	2.91	20.78

Cotham Member					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	16.68	3	2.66	14.59	19.68
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	19.27	6	9.50	5.77	31.16
<i>Isocyprina concentricum</i> (Moore)	6.31	6	2.53	4.12	10.03
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	3.99	9	1.31	2.43	5.82
<i>Mytilus cloacinus</i> Tutcher	4.17	5	3.66	1.93	10.60
<i>Placunopsis alpina</i> (Winkler)	7.24	5	2.04	4.68	9.37
<i>Pleuromya</i> sp.	19.21	2	8.13	13.46	24.96
<i>Protocardia rhaetica</i> (Merian)	10.72	5	3.25	6.72	14.20
<i>Pteromya crowcombeia</i> Moore	10.80	36	7.12	2.13	27.96
<i>Rhaetavicula contorta</i> (Portlock)	8.79	1	***	8.79	8.79

Langport Member					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Astarte</i> sp.	8.83	1	***	8.83	8.83
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	16.78	20	6.37	7.29	33.48
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	15.84	5	8.09	8.46	26.25
<i>Gervillella ornata</i> Moore	6.09	1	***	6.09	6.09
<i>Grammatodon hettangiensis</i> (Terquem)	14.33	1	***	14.33	14.33
<i>Isocyprina concentricum</i> (Moore)	8.28	71	2.57	3.45	17.15
<i>Liostrea bristovi</i> (Richardson)	19.07	30	4.27	11.69	26.58
<i>Liostrea hisingeri</i> (Nilsson)	17.80	12	6.16	7.90	25.46
<i>Mesomiltha</i> sp.	8.15	2	2.26	6.56	9.75
<i>Modiolus hillanus</i> (J. Sowerby)	13.38	16	4.76	4.71	20.55
<i>Modiolus minimus</i> (J. Sowerby)	8.39	3	3.99	5.07	12.81
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	6.86	17	3.17	3.65	16.61
<i>Pholadomya</i> sp.	19.07	7	4.68	11.59	25.52
<i>Plagiostoma giganteum</i> J. Sowerby	19.09	10	5.20	11.81	29.32
<i>Pleuromya</i> sp.	18.72	40	6.14	7.86	38.74
<i>Protocardia rhaetica</i> (Merian)	13.36	50	3.88	4.95	25.31
<i>Pseudolimea duplicata</i> (Sowerby)	11.08	1	***	11.08	11.08
<i>Pteromya crowcombeia</i> Moore	12.53	1	***	12.53	12.53
<i>Pteromya langportensis</i> (Richardson & Tutcher)	10.92	16	3.74	5.33	18.68

Pre-Planorbis Zone					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	16.96	46	6.08	7.09	39.81
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	10.27	18	8.71	2.44	33.92
<i>Gervillella ornata</i> Moore	18.87	5	2.46	16.29	21.96
<i>Liostrea hisingeri</i> (Nilsson)	16.74	136	7.49	4.33	41.22
<i>Modiolus hillanus</i> (J. Sowerby)	15.49	11	5.04	6.79	21.45
<i>Modiolus minimus</i> (J. Sowerby)	6.04	98	3.23	2.01	21.77
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	7.31	78	3.29	1.31	15.09
<i>Myoconcha psilonoti</i> Quenstedt	10.35	7	4.98	4.45	20.49
<i>Oxytoma fallax</i> (Pflücker)	9.13	8	12.15	2.54	38.60
<i>Pholadomya</i> sp.	23.55	8	5.78	14.62	31.96
<i>Plagiostoma giganteum</i> J. Sowerby	28.97	7	10.67	15.60	44.69
<i>Pleuromya</i> sp.	16.61	15	7.55	5.42	35.38
<i>Protocardia rhaetica</i> (Merian)	10.54	1	***	10.54	10.54
<i>Pseudolimea duplicata</i> (Sowerby)	19.23	1	***	19.23	19.23
<i>Pteromya crowcombeia</i> Moore	15.89	11	6.78	10.75	34.79
<i>Pteromya langportensis</i> (Richardson & Tutcher)	12.66	28	4.98	6.05	26.73
<i>Ryderia</i> cf. <i>texturata</i> (Terquem & Piette)	10.92	4	6.69	3.84	19.51

Planorbis Zone					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Camptonectes</i> sp.	14.47	3	4.19	9.80	17.88
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	13.77	126	8.07	2.77	60.98
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	17.05	14	10.02	6.19	36.35
<i>Liostrea hisingeri</i> (Nilsson)	15.66	102	6.13	4.23	37.15
<i>Modiolus hillanus</i> (J. Sowerby)	7.82	12	3.73	2.52	14.75
<i>Modiolus minimus</i> (J. Sowerby)	5.45	109	2.83	2.12	17.56
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	6.82	40	2.64	2.55	12.82
<i>Modiolus ventricosus</i> (Roener)	5.51	90	1.82	2.45	11.23
<i>Oxytoma fallax</i> (Pflücker)	2.20	1	***	2.20	2.20
<i>Palaeoneilo elliptica</i> (Goldfuss)	4.49	12	1.13	3.13	5.90
<i>Palaeonucula navis</i> (Piette)	20.32	5	17.05	2.45	47.65
<i>Pholadomya</i> sp.	29.27	8	9.09	14.20	39.96
<i>Plagiostoma giganteum</i> J. Sowerby	30.92	40	16.91	8.20	65.90
<i>Pleuromya</i> sp.	5.73	4	3.01	2.06	8.33
<i>Pseudolimea duplicata</i> (Sowerby)	4.78	2	1.77	3.53	6.02
? <i>Pteromya</i> sp.	12.14	14	5.56	6.97	22.42
<i>Rollieria bronni</i> (Anderl)	20.65	1	***	20.65	20.65
<i>Ryderia</i> cf. <i>texturata</i> (Terquem & Piette)	8.17	2	4.43	5.03	11.30

Liasicus Zone					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Camptonectes</i> sp.	10.47	10	3.04	6.48	14.89
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	14.13	20	8.63	4.13	43.01
<i>Chlamys valoniensis</i> (Defrance in Caumont)	9.65	3	5.39	3.81	14.43
<i>Gervillella ornata</i> Moore	18.70	2	1.20	17.85	19.55
<i>Grammatodon hettangiensis</i> (Terquem)	16.19	3	11.68	6.45	29.14
<i>Liostrea hisingeri</i> (Nilsson)	15.13	17	8.39	3.97	36.33
<i>Mactromya cardioides</i> Phillips	25.85	5	16.97	9.26	53.68
<i>Modiolus</i> sp.	6.88	22	4.85	1.62	16.47
<i>Modiolus ventricosus</i> (Roener)	6.39	23	4.12	1.97	15.97
<i>Palaeonucula navis</i> (Piette)	4.69	6	1.45	3.21	7.15
<i>Pholadomya</i> sp.	11.68	3	6.81	4.92	18.54
<i>Placunopsis alpina</i> (Winkler)	9.16	1	***	9.16	9.16
<i>Plagiostoma giganteum</i> J. Sowerby	37.22	20	25.84	2.69	96.32
<i>Pseudolimea duplicata</i> (Sowerby)	5.81	4	1.07	4.24	6.52
<i>Rollieria bronni</i> (Anderl)	6.66	1	***	6.66	6.66
<i>Ryderia</i> cf. <i>texturata</i> (Terquem & Piette)	27.10	2	6.91	22.22	31.99

Angulata Zone					
Species	Mean	n	S.D.	Min.	Max.
<i>Camptonectes sp.</i>	8.31	4	2.77	4.33	10.64
<i>Cardinia regularis</i> Terquem	18.88	12	4.29	10.50	25.74
<i>Gryphaea obliquata</i> Sowerby	13.91	11	12.85	4.60	42.89
<i>Liostrea hisingeri</i> (Nilsson)	16.65	22	6.76	7.72	39.38
<i>Modiolus hillanus</i> (J. Sowerby)	19.05	1	***	19.05	19.05
<i>Modiolus sp.</i>	8.43	5	2.17	5.85	10.71
<i>Modiolus ventricosus</i> (Roener)	6.50	3	0.21	6.32	6.73
<i>Myoconcha psilonoti</i> Quenstedt	20.69	7	8.10	13.98	34.93
<i>Pseudolimea duplicata</i> (Sowerby)	8.46	5	3.86	4.66	12.65

Supplementary Table 2. Test of homogeneity of variances performed to compare the variance between localities. PB: Pinhay Bay, NI: Larne, Northern Ireland and AB: St.

Audrie's Bay.. df: degree of freedom. P: Probability value, critical $\alpha = 0.05$. All comparisons were non-significant.

Stratigraphic unit	Localities	df	Bartlett (chi-X^2)
Westbury Fm.	AB vs. NI	1	1.05
Cotham Member	AB vs. NI	1	0.81
Langport Member	AB vs. NI vs. PB	2	2.31
Pre-Planorbis Zone	AB vs. NI vs. PB	2	2.94
Planorbis Zone	AB vs. NI vs. PB	2	1.83
Liasicus Zone	AB vs. NI vs. PB	2	0.33
Angulata Zone	AB vs. PB	1	0.05

Supplementary Table 3. Results of the autocorrelogram used to evaluate the existence of phylogenetic inertia on species body size. P value: Probability value, critical $\alpha = 0.05$.

Variance source	Rescaled Moran's I	P value
Genus	0.42	0.16
Family	0.22	0.44
Order	-0.06	0.85

Supplementary Table 4. Statistical descriptors of the body size distribution for each

mode of life and stratigraphic unit. WF= Westbury Formation, CM= Cotham Member,

LM= Langport Member, PPZ= Pre-Planorbis Zone, PZ= Planorbis Zone, LZ= Liasicus Zone,

AZ= Angulata. Modes of life in superscript, Inf= Infaunal, Semi=Semi-Infaunal,

Sur=Surficial. N=Number of individuals. $\bar{X}$ = Mean. Min= Minimum. Max=Maximum. 5%=

5% of interval confidence. 95%= 95% of interval confidence. CV= Coefficient of variation.

SK=Skewness. K=Kurtosis. S-W= Shapiro-Wilk W statistic values. (*): Significant

probability value (not normal), critic $\alpha = 0.05$.

FM	N	$\bar{X}$	Min.	Max.	5%	95%	CV	SK	K	KS	SW
WF ^{Inf}	170	3.61	0.15	5.48	3.05	4.31	31.17	0.08	-1.04	0.79	0.86*
WF ^{Semi}	121	3.01	0.18	4.74	2.62	3.69	33.14	0.09	-1.23	1.22	0.87*
WF ^{Sur}	313	3.12	0.19	5.27	2.68	3.86	34.78	0.06	-0.72	0.64	0.95*
CM ^{Inf}	51	3.73	0.76	6.59	2.72	4.78	34.97	0.18	0.06	-0.25	0.94*
CM ^{Semi}	9	1.96	1.28	2.54	1.50	2.31	25.62	0.17	-0.22	-1.87	0.89
CM ^{Sur}	13	3.05	0.95	4.96	2.53	3.69	38.22	0.32	-0.01	-0.19	0.97
LM ^{Inf}	208	3.43	0.17	5.28	2.94	3.98	25.19	0.06	-1.21	2.83	0.92*
LM ^{Semi}	31	3.67	2.11	5.30	3.17	4.08	19.40	0.13	-0.37	0.52	0.94*
LM ^{Sur}	59	3.93	1.22	4.87	3.72	4.54	21.13	0.11	-2.02	4.28	0.76*
PPZ ^{Inf}	107	3.45	0.28	5.32	3.09	4.24	35.49	0.12	-1.20	0.62	0.86*
PPZ ^{Semi}	199	2.58	0.23	4.82	1.91	3.19	34.79	0.06	-0.28	-0.24	0.98*
PPZ ^{Sur}	168	3.76	0.54	6.04	3.28	4.43	31.34	0.09	-0.77	0.73	0.92*
PZ ^{Inf}	190	3.28	0.43	6.12	2.57	4.03	32.80	0.08	-0.30	-0.13	0.99
PZ ^{Semi}	252	2.35	0.32	4.13	1.90	2.80	27.50	0.04	-0.15	0.23	0.99
PZ ^{Sur}	163	2.74	0.18	5.21	2.46	3.14	27.91	0.06	-1.23	3.93	0.93*
LZ ^{Inf}	37	2.81	0.22	4.25	2.27	3.69	35.88	0.17	-0.64	0.35	0.94
LZ ^{Semi}	46	2.39	0.28	4.29	1.57	3.16	45.28	0.16	0.11	-1.03	0.96
LZ ^{Sur}	52	2.93	0.28	4.81	1.98	3.90	42.38	0.17	-0.49	-0.74	0.99
AZ ^{Inf}	12	4.20	3.39	4.69	4.00	4.43	8.36	0.10	-0.88	1.56	0.94
AZ ^{Semi}	19	4.03	2.30	5.44	3.58	4.58	17.25	0.16	-0.19	1.31	0.92*
AZ ^{Sur}	27	3.49	2.20	5.42	2.66	4.29	28.00	0.19	0.40	-1.09	0.96

Supplementary Table 5. Results of pairwise Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests performed to compare body size distributions (BSDs) between tiers. Stratigraphic units in superscript:

WF= Westbury Formation, CM= Cotham Member, LM= Langport Member, PPZ= Pre-Planorbis Zone, PZ= Planorbis Zone, LZ= Liasicus Zone, AZ= Angulata Zone.

D=Kolmogorov D statistic values. (*) = significant p-value adjusted by Bonferroni corrections.

	Surficial	Semi-Infaunal
Semi-Infaunal^{WF}	D=0.13	
Infaunal^{WF}	D=0.31*	D=0.36*
Semi-Infaunal^{CM}	D=0.69*	
Infaunal^{CM}	D=0.19	D=0.59*
Semi-Infaunal^{LM}	D=0.58*	
Infaunal^{LM}	D=0.36*	D=0.38*
Semi-Infaunal^{PPZ}	D=0.54*	
Infaunal^{PPZ}	D=0.09	D=0.53*
Semi-Infaunal^{PZ}	D=0.71*	
Infaunal^{PZ}	D=0.24*	D=0.52*
Semi-Infaunal^{LZ}	D=0.44*	
Infaunal^{LZ}	D=0.37*	D=0.72*
Semi-Infaunal^{AZ}	D=0.34	
Infaunal^{AZ}	D=0.52*	D=0.58*

Supplementary Table 7. Observed and randomized body size (mm) per sample. AOD: Average of observed data; 25% Obs and 75% Obs: 25th and 75th percentile of observed data. ANM: Average of null model, 25% NM and 95% NM: 25th and 75th percentile of each null model.

No. Sample	Locality	AOD	25% Obs	75% Obs	ANM	25% NM	75% NM
Sample 1	AB	9.79	12.31	8.02	4.61	4.32	4.90
Sample 2	AB	16.93	21.50	8.98	3.81	3.53	4.08
Sample 3	AB	8.63	9.69	6.31	3.48	3.20	3.75
Sample 4	AB	11.46	13.02	6.77	6.37	6.01	6.70
Sample 5	AB	16.42	23.33	10.45	6.59	6.24	6.92
Sample 6	AB	9.74	11.57	6.94	11.35	10.95	11.75
Sample 7	AB	7.70	10.03	4.32	1.02	0.87	1.14
Sample 8	AB	7.70	10.03	4.32	1.03	0.89	1.14
Sample 9	AB	10.82	13.19	5.51	3.33	3.04	3.56
Sample 10	AB	17.00	20.46	13.93	2.59	2.31	2.81
Sample 11	AB	17.12	20.73	13.39	4.53	4.22	4.82
Sample 12	AB	13.56	16.03	10.39	5.34	5.01	5.63
Sample 13	AB	13.42	18.38	8.26	11.61	11.23	11.98
Sample 14	AB	13.56	15.61	7.32	2.86	2.58	3.09
Sample 15	AB	13.58	16.86	8.99	0.95	0.82	1.06
Sample 16	AB	10.97	13.04	6.93	3.14	2.85	3.40
Sample 17	AB	14.28	17.65	9.36	5.07	4.74	5.38
Sample 18	AB	8.14	10.46	5.47	1.38	1.22	1.51
Sample 19	AB	12.24	16.21	7.66	0.59	0.48	0.67
Sample 20	AB	23.40	25.81	15.45	3.42	3.14	3.67
Sample 21	AB	8.87	9.80	5.96	1.37	1.20	1.51
Sample 22	AB	22.61	31.99	10.22	2.93	2.66	3.18
Sample 23	AB	10.87	8.16	2.45	1.48	1.30	1.64
Sample 24	AB	6.88	7.83	5.96	0.59	0.49	0.67
Sample 25	AB	10.27	11.15	9.40	0.42	0.34	0.48
Sample 26	AB	12.49	11.94	7.24	1.11	0.95	1.23
Sample 27	AB	12.23	14.35	10.00	1.68	1.49	1.84
Sample 28	AB	16.17	18.42	13.77	3.21	2.96	3.48
Sample 1	NI	5.65	6.23	5.38	0.59	0.50	0.67
Sample 2	NI	5.65	6.23	5.38	0.58	0.48	0.67
Sample 3	NI	8.73	8.99	6.64	4.62	4.30	4.91
Sample 4	NI	6.86	7.80	5.69	2.95	2.68	3.20
Sample 5	NI	8.65	11.32	5.78	3.90	3.58	4.16
Sample 6	NI	9.94	12.47	7.69	7.97	7.58	8.33
Sample 7	NI	3.25	3.24	2.56	0.66	0.56	0.75

Sample 8	NI	6.82	9.37	3.43	1.39	1.21	1.54
Sample 9	NI	14.05	16.33	11.41	0.86	0.73	0.95
Sample 10	NI	11.17	16.47	3.82	3.33	3.04	3.59
Sample 11	NI	13.41	15.01	11.22	2.74	2.48	2.97
Sample 12	NI	15.68	19.07	12.00	1.29	1.13	1.43
Sample 13	NI	15.30	20.23	10.20	1.19	1.04	1.32
Sample 14	NI	17.85	19.62	13.49	4.32	4.02	4.62
Sample 15	NI	16.04	17.63	14.73	1.60	1.40	1.76
Sample 16	NI	16.91	19.46	12.00	2.94	2.68	3.18
Sample 17	NI	15.87	21.44	10.26	1.60	1.41	1.75
Sample 18	NI	4.04	4.75	2.60	3.82	3.53	4.09
Sample 19	NI	7.42	9.55	4.32	2.81	2.56	3.05
Sample 20	NI	4.33	4.54	2.84	5.74	5.42	6.03
Sample 21	NI	6.54	6.95	3.71	4.20	3.90	4.47
Sample 22	NI	6.05	7.02	4.62	5.68	5.33	6.01
Sample 23	NI	4.56	5.08	3.18	1.28	1.13	1.42
Sample 24	NI	13.28	21.98	4.54	1.60	1.41	1.77
Sample 25	NI	7.92	7.73	4.55	1.20	1.04	1.32
Sample 26	NI	8.29	9.12	5.60	2.56	2.30	2.79
Sample 27	NI	12.69	16.27	7.33	7.05	6.70	7.37
Sample 28	NI	5.06	5.39	4.45	0.59	0.49	0.68
Sample 29	NI	13.17	13.99	11.57	0.59	0.48	0.67
Sample 30	NI	12.13	14.82	7.49	0.94	0.80	1.06
Sample 31	NI	11.70	6.89	3.69	0.85	0.72	0.95
Sample 32	NI	5.17	5.88	4.53	0.68	0.56	0.78
Sample 33	NI	38.89	55.15	13.30	0.86	0.71	0.97
Sample 1	PB	8.32	8.32	5.31	1.09	0.95	1.21
Sample 2	PB	6.69	6.69	6.69	0.33	0.26	0.38
Sample 3	PB	9.32	9.77	7.25	4.02	3.72	4.28
Sample 4	PB	8.58	10.42	6.06	3.75	3.45	4.03
Sample 5	PB	10.37	15.22	3.50	4.70	4.40	4.97
Sample 6	PB	17.18	23.11	9.71	4.96	4.63	5.26
Sample 7	PB	11.92	11.12	7.68	4.79	4.49	5.08
Sample 8	PB	12.00	14.80	6.19	7.75	7.36	8.09
Sample 9	PB	29.48	39.96	17.94	2.21	1.98	2.42
Sample 10	PB	19.99	22.90	13.69	2.12	1.89	2.34
Sample 11	PB	26.06	29.89	17.91	1.70	1.49	1.87
Sample 12	PB	8.27	13.33	3.65	1.28	1.11	1.42
Sample 13	PB	14.56	18.70	8.13	1.60	1.41	1.76
Sample 14	PB	8.75	13.75	3.42	0.68	0.57	0.78
Sample 15	PB	13.36	19.03	7.88	1.59	1.39	1.75
Sample 16	PB	14.30	19.83	6.38	2.39	2.14	2.63